

CRITICAL IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON DIFFERENT PROPERTIES OF WEED, HERBICIDE AND THEIR VULNERABILITIES AND CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract

Global climate change and its consequences such as rising temperatures, carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels, variable rainfall and soil salinity has an impact on weed species, their population dynamics, reproduction and competitive ability; eventually crop productivity. Among these environmental factors, rising CO₂ levels will benefit C₃ plants, but in the near future, plants with C₄ pathways will be benefited more from rising temperatures and changing rainfall patterns around the world. Climate change can alter the weed life cycle, community composition, distribution, phenology and infestation. Over the course of the year, some weed species go extinct while others develop into more noxious invaders and evolve genetic artefacts in response to intensifying climatic and non-climatic selection pressures. Due to unfavourable climatic change, weed species release allelo chemicals along with increase the growth of below ground part such as root or rhizome, particularly in perennial weeds, making the weed more competitive over crops. On the solution side, variations in temperature, CO₂ levels and rainfall alter stomatal conductance, cuticle viscosity, transport, uptake, leaf retention duration and herbicide efficacy. Therefore, to adapt and mitigate; it is important to review how climate change can influence the crop-weed interaction, competition, herbicide efficacy and resistance.

Keywords: Climate Change, Herbicide Efficacy, Population Dynamics, Weed Shift, Weed Management

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1. Introduction

Climate change is defined as any shift in the state of the climate identified by fluctuations in the mean and/or variability of its properties caused by natural or anthropogenic activities that lasts for a longer period of time, such as decades or more (IPCC, 2014; Aggarwal and Pasricha, 2011). During the past 70 years, shifting towards modern agriculture has been the principal driving factor for climate change, accounting for approximately 30% of greenhouse gas emissions (Nitze et al., 2018). With this unpredictable change in climate, it is predicted that the world's population will reach 10 billion by 2050 (UN, 2019). Therefore, the global challenge for food producers, researchers and policymakers will be to provide enough high-quality food for the expanding human population. Climate change increased atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels from 280 to 421 ppm between 1750 and 2022; at this rate of increase, global CO₂ concentration is expected to reach around 600 ppm by 2050 (Waterhouse, 1994; Dukes et al., 1999). In addition, climate models predicted that rising CO₂ concentrations would cause the earth's surface temperature to rise from 1.1 to 6.4°C during the 21st century (IPCC, 2004). Similarly, the average rainfall during the months of wet and winter season is anticipated to rise up to 20% by the year 2070 and there is a higher probability that climate extremes, such as drought and floods, will occur (Khan et al., 2009). The stability of ecosystems will be

significantly impacted by extreme weather events and abrupt climate changes, which will change plant life and the agricultural system. Weeds are the primary agricultural pest for crops, as weeds cause a loss of approximately 34% of crop yield (Anwar et al., 2021). Climatic conditions have a substantial impact on the distribution, population dynamics and life cycle length of agricultural pests, both directly and indirectly via temperature, CO₂ increase and sea level rise. Weeds are able to survive in a variety of challenging environmental conditions in crop fields or other disturbed ecosystems due to wide ecological amplitudes and a set of distinctive biological traits like competitiveness, aggressive behaviour, adaptability and high fecundity (Fleming et al., 2010; Chandrasena, 2009). For example, previously relatively insignificant weeds are becoming regionally important species now. As illustrated in the Table 1, variations in temperature and other climatic factors are likely to modify the ecosystem of different weeds at lower latitudes and altitudes.

In addition to the effect of climate change on the distribution, ecology and composition of weed, it also alters the efficacy of weed management. Warmer and wetter condition modify the chemical characteristic of specific herbicides, altering their efficacy, distribution and translocation on weeds (Poorter and Navas, 2003; Dukes et al., 2009). Herbicide efficacy is affected by a number of factors, such as CO₂ concentration, temperature, rainfall, wind and relative humidity, either directly by modifying herbicide penetration and translocation in target plants or indirectly by changing the growth and physiological characteristics of the plants (Carlson et al., 1980). In order to create practical weed management strategies in the context of a changing climate, it is therefore necessary to investigate crop-weed competition.

Table 1. Potential Effects of Climate Change on Various Weeds Important to Agriculture

Scientific Name	Habitat and nature of the weed	Expected impact of climate change	Reference
<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	In most of Europe, <i>Rubus fruticosus</i> is a native plant. In addition to being on the federal noxious weed list in the USA, it is listed as a "weed of national significance" in Australia.	As it is susceptible to drought and warmer temperatures, expected to retreat higher altitudes	(Anon, 2004)
<i>Lantana camara</i>	The native range of <i>Lantana camara</i> is Central and South America. A wide-ranging species found predominantly in tropical and subtropical environments.	Due to its sensitivity to drought, it is anticipated to retreat southward.	(Bhagwat et al. 2012)
<i>Prosopis glandulosa</i>	The shrub or small tree <i>Prosopis glandulosa</i> is indigenous to Mexico, Central America and northern South America. It has proven to be a very aggressive invader, particularly in its native range's frost-free arid and semiarid natural grasslands.	It is anticipated to continue shifting southward into an area with heavy rainfall. Due to its extreme tolerance to drought, there is some risk that it may move to regions with lower rainfall.	(Hussain et al. 2021)
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>	Mexico in Central America is the native of <i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> a weed of the subtropical, tropical and warmer temperate zones. It can be found near waterways, railroad tracks and roadside ditches. It is particularly aggressive in disturbed or degraded pastures in semi-arid climates.	Not suitable for regions with predominant winter rainfall, may shift to regions with predominant summer high rainfall (> 500mm)	(Adkins and Shabbir 2014)

<i>Nassella trichotoma</i>	Southern South America is the native environment of <i>Nassella trichotoma</i> . a weed found in semi-arid and temperate climates. Common habitats for its growth include pastures, grasslands, open woods and drier forests (particularly in highland areas).	As it is sensitive to temperature as a drought-tolerant plant, it is anticipated to retreat southward and to higher altitudes	(Laffan, 2006).
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2. Impact of Climate Change on Weed Ecology, Distribution and Resistance

Extreme weather events like storms, severe droughts and extreme cold spells are predicted to occur more frequently as a result of climate change. Weed will likely to be benefitted much over the crop as a result of these seasonal changes in the local climate with greater amplitudes. In summary, C₃ plants benefit physiologically from rising CO₂ levels, but photosynthesis of C₄ plants is more efficient than that of C₃ plants at higher temperatures (Coumou, 2012; Walther et al., 2002; Carter, 1983). Although C₄ weeds predominate in agriculture, C₃ and C₃-C₄ intermediary weeds would pose a serious crop-weed competition in the years to come. Because of this species interaction, there is an urgent need to explore all possible plant-weed-climate-human continuum combinations (Tubiello, 2007; Upasani and Barla, 2018).

2.1. Direct Effect of Climate Change

2.1.1. Weed Response to Elevated CO₂ Concentration

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (UN-IPCC) predicts that atmospheric CO₂ concentrations will exceed 700 ppm by the end of the 21st century (Houghton et al., 1996). Among the 18 most troublesome weeds, 14 are C₄ and in this elevated situation C₃ weeds are more responsive to CO₂ enhancement thus, crop-weed competition will be altered in the near future (Holm et al., 1997; Mishra, 2003). Over the past three decades, numerous studies have been carried out to determine the effects of elevated atmospheric CO₂ on weeds with C₃ and C₄ photosynthetic pathways. All of the studies concluded that CO₂ enrichment is more likely to benefit C₃ photosynthetic plants over C₄ plants (Patterson and Flint, 1980). Enhancing the CO₂ concentration resulted in a 39% increase in C₃ weed growth compared to 18% increase in C₄ weed growth (Poorter, 1993). As a result, if the C₄ weeds are less susceptible to increased CO₂ level then, C₃ weed species are more likely to respond. At ambient and elevated CO₂ levels (ambient +250 ppm) interactions between soybean and two weed species, *Chenopodium album* (C₃) and *Amaranthus retro-flexus* (C₄) (Ziska and Caulfield, 2000) suggests that *C. album* would benefit more from elevated conditions than soybean and might even become a more dominant weed; on the contrary *Amaranthus retro-flexus* would benefit less from increased CO₂ levels and soybean has the competitive advantage in a mixed flora (Table 2) (Ziska and Caulfield, 2000; Singh et al., 2016). Along with the high CO₂ concentration C₃ weeds are more water-efficient (biomass is increased more than water used) thus potentially allowing C₃ weeds into drier habitats in the near future (Peters et al., 2014; Kriticos et al., 2003). However, on the other hand, the effect of increased CO₂ on competition between a C₃ crop (*Oryza sativa*) and a C₄ weed (*Echinochloa crus-galli*). suggest that, rice (C₃) had significantly higher biomass, tillers, leaf area index and net assimilation rate than barnyard grass at elevated CO₂ (ambient + 250 ppm) (C₄) (Table 2) (Zeng et al., 2011). Increasing CO₂ favours the growth of C₃-C₄ intermediate weed; for example, the impact of high CO₂ concentration on growth and production of *Parthenium hysterophorus* (C₃-C₄ intermediate weed) concluded that in parthenium, elevated CO₂ caused plants to grow taller (43% more), produce more leaves (17% more), flowers early and produce more biomass (30%) than ambient CO₂ (Bajwa et al., 2019). Weeds are more genetically diverse than crops and many of them reproduce vegetatively

(through roots, stolons, etc.). As per recent research, these weeds may collectively exhibit a strong response to the rise in CO₂. Since perennial weeds usually spread through underground parts, they may subsequently become even more invasive in response to rising CO₂. The effects of elevated CO₂ on soil enzyme activities in weeds connected to the rice-wheat ecosystem concluded that CO₂ enrichment significantly increased soil enzymes like dehydrogenase, fluorescein diacetate hydrolysis and urease activity in the rhizosphere of weeds particularly in comparison to rice and wheat (Sarathambal et al., 2016; Hobbs and Gupta, 2003). Carbon dioxide enrichment advanced the maturation of *Avena fatua* seeds, as per research conducted in Open Top Chambers (OTCs) at the Directorate of Weed Research, Jabalpur, India. The seeds matured 13 days earlier than plants grown in ambient CO₂ conditions, which may result in soil seed bank enrichment (Naidu, 2015). Weed with high CO₂ fixation rate and other features such as shorter life cycles, vegetative reproduction, or spread seeds would become extremely competitive and invade more in crop field near future.

Table 2. Crop-Weed Interaction at Elevated CO₂ Level

Crop species	Weed species	Normal situation	Effect of elevated CO ₂	Reference
Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>) (C ₃)	Red rice (<i>Oryza sativa spontanea</i>) (C ₃)	For every red rice plant /m ² , there is a 100–755 kg /ha reduction in rice yield.	Under conditions of high CO ₂ levels, red rice is more competitive than cultivated rice.	(Ziska et al. 2010)
Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>) (C ₃)	<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> (C ₄)	Drastically affect the rice and may result in a yield loss of 21–79% for rice.	A C ₃ crop may compete better against a C ₄ weed when CO ₂ levels are elevated alone, but simultaneous increases in CO ₂ and temperature may favour the C ₄ weed.	(Alberto et al. 1996; Bhowmik and Reddy 1988)
Soybean (<i>Glycine max</i>) (C ₃)	<i>Chenopodium album</i> (C ₃) and <i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> (C ₄)	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> (C ₄) affect more than <i>Chenopodium album</i> (C ₃)	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> would benefit less from increased CO ₂ and <i>C. album</i> would benefit more than soybean. As a result, <i>C. album</i> might gain popularity.	(Ziska 2000)

The average global temperature is expected to rise by 2.4–6.4°C by the 21st century, as stated by the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (Waterhouse, 1994). The distribution of weed species in a particular geographic area is significantly influenced by the temperature. As a result of temperature enhancement, some new weeds may become more abundant, exhibit different competing behaviours and displace native weeds and spread into different uninhabited areas. Therefore, a shift in weed distribution to high latitudes and altitudes has an impact on the most important cropping systems, such as rice- and maize-based cropping systems (Knapp et al., 1993). As a result of synchronising its flowering and fruiting times with the emergence of maize, *Setaria viridis*, which would be a troublesome weed in maize-based cropping systems, germinated later in the (August) season under warmer conditions (Ramesh et al., 2017; Dekker, 2003). It is observed that a 4°C increase in temperature accelerated flowering by 26 and 35 days in *C. album* (C₃) and *S. viridis* (C₄), respectively (Lee, 2011). It means that C₄ weed species can withstand greater temperature changes than C₃ weed species. In a comparative study on the effect of temperature in growth and competitiveness of soybean,

Amaranthus viridis (C₄) and *Xanthium strumarium* (C₃) revealed that the growth is higher and relative competitiveness is more in *Amaranthus viridis* than *Xanthium strumarium* with soybean (Flint and Patterson, 1983). Even under stress, the C₄ pathway of *Amaranthus viridis* helps in better temperature utilization and boosts growth (Mandal et al., 2017). Similarly, it was found that *Lantana camara* would become more invasive and competitive as a result of global warming and showed increased leaf area (2 times) and stem length (4 times) at elevated temperature (30°C) than at normal (22°C) (Mary, 2021). The most potentially invasive feature of the weed is that a greater proportion of assimilates are partitioning towards the root, resulting in unusual enlargement in the root mass with rich food reserves, providing rapid and robust regeneration even at high temperatures (Kriticos et al., 2010). Greater increases in root biomass are observed in regions with higher mean annual temperatures than in regions with lower mean annual temperatures (Patterson et al., 1999; Stitt, 1991). Thus, due to the increase in root biomass, the ability of the weed to withstand climatic extremes, such as peak summer droughts, water stress and flooding is increased.

2.1.2. Weed Response to Variable Rainfall

Climate change is expected to cause variations in the amount and distribution of global precipitation, making future rainfall predictions uncertain. Unpredictable rainfall, drought and flooding would become regular events, making weed distribution, competition, interaction and prevalence in crop ecosystems challenging. Rainfall variability indicates that, the monsoon regions will become more drier, resulting in a 10-20% increase in drought-prone areas (Giannini et al., 2008; Rodenburg, et al., 2011). In this irregular rainfall, upland rice and rainfed lowland rice encounter serious competition from C₄ weeds, as most weeds in rice ecosystems are C₄ and yield is affected drastically, as shown in Figure 1. Direct seeded rice (DSR) continues to experience higher yield losses than transplanted rice (TPR); a 35% loss has been reported in TPR. However, in DSR, it could reach 100%. Various pests responsible for the full 40% yield loss in rice account for nearly 10% of the TPR and 32% of the DSR. Leaf area and total dry weight of three C₄ grasses like *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Digitaria ciliaris* and *Eleusine indica* are significantly increased by drought stress in rice eco-system with variable rainfall (Blumenthal et al., 2008). In South Asia, a switch from transplanting to direct seeding of rice to save water has already resulted in increased weed competition (sometime up to 100% crop loss) and altered weed dynamics (Matloob et al., 2015a). Even at the lower soil water content, *Amaranthus spinosus* and *Leptochloa chinensis* thrived and produced many tillers/branches and leaves than rice (Mooney and Hobbs, 2000). Ratio of biomass between *Echinochloa colona* and rice increased from 4.7 at 100% of field capacity (FC) to 7.6 at 12.5% FC, showing enhanced weed vigour under water stress conditions (Chauhan and Johnson, 2010). In several places of India, the rainfall pattern is gradually changing. Range land weeds such as cheat grass (*Bromus tectorum*) and yellow star thistle (*Centaurea solstitialis*) rely on soil moisture for seed germination; thus, higher soil moisture due to prolonged rain increases the seed production of both species (Udayashankara et al., 2016; Patterson, 1995). *Lantana camara*, for example, could expand if rainfall increased in some areas (Rana and Rana, 2016). To reduce flood-induced stress, certain weed species have developed avoidance, escape or quiescence strategies. In order to avoid flooding, weeds can complete their life cycle between two subsequent flood events and these flood periods are survived by dormant life stages (e.g., *Chenopodium rubrum*). *Cyperus rotundus* can alter their metabolic or morphological growth processes in flooded soils and make them more adapted to the flooded condition of paddy fields by increasing the cross-sectional area of the stem occupied aerenchyma tissue in low land conditions twice that of the species in upland conditions (Fuentes et al., 2010). However, *Alternanthera philoxeroides* can maintain the integrity of the photosynthetic apparatus under stress and recover quickly from

submergence. As a result, a sizeable portion of the carbohydrates will be set aside for post-submergence activity, making it a waterproof plant (Ye et al., 2016). A phyto-sociological analysis of the floristic composition of weeds in the Cauvery River delta region of Tamil Nadu state revealed that due to increased precipitation, alien invasive weeds *Leptochloa chinensis* and *Marsilea quadrifolia* entered rice fields (Joos et al., 2001; Naidu, 2015). Due to their amphibious adaptation to the alternating flooded and residual soil moisture condition, these two weed species predominate over native weeds like *Echinochloa* spp. and others (Yaduraju and Kathiresan, 2003). A general conclusion that can be drawn from the above- mentioned explanation is that increased rainfall would lead to an increase in weed pressure, an increase in the cost of herbicides and an overall increase in the cost of production.

DSR: direct seeded rice; TPR: transplanted rice; RU: rainfed upland; RL: rainfed lowland; IWS: irrigated wet system

Figure 1: The magnitude of yield losses of DSR caused by weeds in different rice-growing ecosystem

Table 3. The impact of increased CO₂ and temperature on major C₃ and C₄ weeds

Photosynthetic pathway	Species	Common name	Effect of elevated CO ₂	Effect of rise in temperature
C ₃ type	<i>Avena fatua</i>	Wild oat	High stimulation of photosynthesis and growth with low photorespiration	Oxygen has a high affinity for the photosynthetic enzyme Rubisco at high temperatures and light levels. Instead of CO ₂ , O ₂ binds to the Rubisco, reducing plant growth via photorespiration.
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	Lambsquarters		
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Canada thistle		
	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	Velvetleaf		
	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	Field bindweed		
	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Cocklebur		
	<i>Agropyron repens</i>	Quack grass		
	<i>Bromus tectorum</i>	Cheatgrass		

C ₄ type	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	Johnsongrass	Lower stimulation of photosynthesis and growth as the CO ₂ compensation rate is very much low around 0-10 ppm and greater efficiency of CO ₂ fixation through PEP	In environments with high temperatures, bright light and low soil moisture plant with C ₄ photosynthesis became benefited.
	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	Shatter cane		
	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	Goosegrass		
	<i>Echinochloa crusgalli</i>	Barnyard grass		
	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	Large crabgrass		
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	Redroot pigweed		
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Bermudagrass		
	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	Purple nutsedge		
	<i>Amaranthus palmeri</i>	Palmer amaranth		

2.1.3. Weed Response to Integrated Effect of CO₂ and Temperature

As illustrated in Table 3, based on the differences in optimum temperature of C₄ spp. and C₃ spp. for physiological activities, C₄ spp. able to withstand higher temperatures than C₃ spp. As a result, increased temperatures linked with elevated CO₂ levels may benefit C₄ weeds more than C₃ crops (Naidu, 2015). As most weeds are C₄ and most crops are C₃ thus expected temperature changes favour weed shift and weed dominance (Hayman and Sadras, 2006). An experimental finding concluded that when only elevated CO₂ was taken into account rice has more competitive advantage than C₄ weed (*Echinochloa glabrescens*) (Alberto et al., 1996). However, when both elevated CO₂ and elevated temperature were taken into account, rice was found to be less competitive than C₄ weed. Another recent study found that the estimated maximum dry weight of rice at ambient+3.4°C was 30.4% higher, while the dry weights of annual and perennial weeds *Echinochloa spp*, *Ludwigia spp*, *Scirpus planiculmis* and *Eleocharis kuroguwa* were 78.2, 211.8, 63.2 and 124% higher respectively.

2.1.4. Weed Response to Integrated Effect of Rainfall and Temperature

Temperature and rainfall variations caused by climate change have a direct impact on germination and the geo-temporal emergence of weed seeds and seedlings. For example, weed dormancy is likely to be broken earlier or sooner than normal due to increased moisture availability, warmer temperatures and moisture.

2.1.5. Weed Response to Integrated Effect of Rainfall, CO₂ and Temperature

Benefits of CO₂ fertilization for growth will be countered by a rise in temperature and accompanying soil moisture stress; the final result will depend on the severity of the moisture stress (Gillham et al., 2009). Plants with C₄ photosynthetic metabolism boost photosynthesis and growth under high CO₂ concentrations in dry environments. Wheat plant increased the biomass against *Phalaris minor* as a result of CO₂ enrichment but under water stress and increased temperature circumstances *Phalaris minor* surpassed the wheat growth (Naidu and Varshney, 2011). Patterson (1986) discovered that increased CO₂ levels favoured the growth of a C₃ crop (soybean) as well as the C₄ weeds *Echinochloa crusgalli*, *Eleusine indica* and *Digitaria ciliaris* by boosting water-use efficiency under drought conditions. However, growth acceleration in the C₃ weed is higher than C₄. It could be speculated that increased CO₂ decrease water use efficiency of the C₄ weeds relative to C₃ crops as the biomass yield is more in C₃ than C₄ weeds; however, C₄ weeds could still potentially compete with C₃ crops under drought situation as C₄ weeds are more adapted towards water stress condition.

2.1.6. Effect of Climate Change on Weed Shift and Seed Bank of Weed

Climate change is expected to affect weed community composition, population dynamics, life cycles, phenology, seed banks and invasiveness. Some weed species may become extinct, while others become more invasive. Climate change causes shifts at three different scales: range shifts at the landscape scale, niche shifts at the community scale and trait shifts of individual species at the population level (Peters et al., 2014). *Striga asiatica*, a root parasite of maize and sorghum may spread from the coastal plains of North and South Carolina and establish itself in the Corn Belt of the United States as a result of climate change-caused range shifts in weed distribution and abundance (Ziska, 2010). The competitive equilibrium between C₃ and C₄ plants is altered by niche shifts caused by global climatic fluctuations, which also affect seasonal niche separation, species distribution patterns and net primary production in mixed communities (Alberto et al., 1996). On the other hand, due to the heavy use of different herbicide along with environmental alterations cause trait shift within the population level making weed management less effective.

Weeds are more diversified and can adapt to different environments, so they can be recruited and germinate faster from the soil seed bank causing natural selection to change and adaptive evolution to occur (Walck et al., 2011; Sakai et al., 2001). Wilson et al. (1985) found that the weed seed bank is made up of a large number of dominant species (70 to 90%), less dominant species or second groups (10 to 20%) and a small portion of the total seed bank (includes recalcitrant seeds from previous seed banks, newly introduced species and seeds of the previous crop). This final group of total seed emerges as the dominant species as a result of significant geographic range expansion or migration changes (Wilson et al., 1985). Thus, changes in the dynamics of weed seed banks makes a weed more successful competitor over crop in the near future.

2.2. Indirect Effect of Climate Change on Weed

Weeds are influenced both directly and indirectly by climate change through crop management and land use. Higher temperatures and other conditions are likely to prolong pollinator (insect) breeding cycles and provide more weed pollination, resulting in a rise in weed population. A rise in CO₂ levels increases pollen production. Increased the concentration of CO₂ increased pollen production of ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*) several times more than normal condition (Boote et al., 2005; Singer et al., 2005). As animals, particularly invasive species migrate to new locations in response to climate change; they are more likely to spread weeds or cause disruptions advantageous to weeds. Climate change make native crop and weed species more vulnerable to weeds by increasing the spread of deadly plant diseases through different emerging weeds.

Table 4. Physiological and ecological characteristics of some weed species in saline condition

Weed name	Salt Tolerance	PS Pathway	Salt Tolerance mechanism	References
<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	ET	C ₃	Morphological changes include larger seeds, effective water availability and use within the plant.	(Eom et al. 2013)
<i>Atriplex prostrata</i>	ET	C ₃	Ability to compartmentalise the harmful ions and maintain adequate concentrations of the essential ions, particularly in the cytoplasm	(Hussein, 2007)
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	MT	C ₄	High water use efficiency, restriction in sodium uptake and high uptake of calcium and potassium	(Mehwish 2017)

<i>Chenopodium album</i>	ET	C ₃	<i>Chenopodium album</i> improves salt tolerance by increasing redox potential in conjunction with high osmolyte and antioxidant production.	(Tanveer and Shah 2017)
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	MT	C ₃	Maintenance of high root area and branches in response to increased salinity provide and acceptable mechanism of salinity tolerance	(Jamshidzadeh et al., 2021)
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	T	C ₄	Because of an increase in proline and other biochemical components and restriction in sodium uptake	(Yamamoto et al., 2003)
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	MT	C ₄	In salt stress, shoots accumulate higher levels of K ⁺ , as indicated by the K ⁺ /Na ⁺ selectivity coefficients.	(Borsai et al. 2020)

* ET=extremely tolerant; MT=moderately tolerant; T=tolerant

Rising sea levels cause an increase in salinity in both surface and ground water due to saltwater intrusion. Table 4 shows that weeds are typically more salt tolerant than crop species. Extreme phenotypic plasticity, allelopathic potential, heteromorphic seed production, seed longevity, quicker emergence and faster crop growth rates in weeds than crop (Ullah et al., 2021; Cirillo et al., 2018). A high salt-tolerant rice cultivar FL 478 did not produce as much shoot biomass in saline soil as *Echinochloa colona* and *Echinochloa crus-galli*. A comparison between *Echinochloa spp* and rice shows that growth of *Echinochloa spp.* will reduce when salinity level is 15-20 dS m⁻¹ but in case of rice it is reduced in just 2 dS m⁻¹ (Cirillo et al., 2018).

On the other hand, during seasons with high to moderate rainfall (precipitation exceeding evapotranspiration), salts are eliminated by deep percolation; hence, pH is decreased by solubilizing more H⁺ and Al ions into the soil solution (Rengel, 2011). Soluble aluminium inhibits plant root growth and reduces the plant's capacity to acquire water and nutrients, yet weed growth is aggressive in this situation. For example, *Rumex acetosella*, *Equisetum arvense*, *Verbascum thapsus* and *Andropogon virginicus* can tolerate acidity more than the crop species in field condition.

3. Weed Management Under Climate Change

3.1. Physical, Mechanical and Cultural Weed Management

Mechanical control is the most popular strategy for weed infestation management in developing countries. Elevated CO₂ levels may cause increased belowground storage and root or rhizome growth, particularly in perennial weeds. As a result, more weeds will propagate from belowground structures and fragments left after mechanical tillage which have detrimental effects on weed management (e.g., *Cirsium arvense*) (Malarkodi et al., 2017; Ziska et al., 2004). Weeds including *Chondrilla juncea* and *Solanum elaeagnifolium* may respond similarly (Darren et al., 2010). To combat this, various cultural approaches provide a possible means of reducing weed pressure. The stale seed bed technique, laser land levelling, zero tillage and competitive cultivars are among the most popular and efficient techniques.

In this changing scenario the cultural/ecological method of weed management is most promising as it helps to increase the crop's competitive behaviour and weed. By using stale seedbed procedures, crop emerges in weed-free conditions, having competitive advantage over late-emerging weed seedlings, reducing weed growth by up to 50% and increasing grain output by 50.7% (Das, 2011). Several studies have found that zero-till fields have lower weed populations than conventional-till fields. Weed suppression is improved by 40 to 60% whenever crop residues are present. Improved microbial activity could also result in weed

suppression along with it can also mitigate climate change by considerably reducing energy input (and thus greenhouse gas emissions) from a particular crop (Nichols et al., 2015). Moisture is distributed evenly across the entire field when the land is levelled properly (Figure 2), promoting uniform crop stand and growth and reducing weed infestation. Weeds can be reduced by up to 45% as a result of improved water coverage by better land levelling (Jat et al., 2006). Development of weed-competitive cultivars and the integration of weed-smothering crops into a cropping system reduce the weed population. Cover crops have the advantage of smothering weeds and invasive plants. Weed density and biomass correlated negatively with cover crop biomass as there is a direct competition between the cover crop and weed for resource as well as allelopathic effect. For example, cover cowpea as a cover crop in maize reduce weed biomass by up to 45% (Jamshidi et al., 2013). There are numerous different weed problems, so there is no one weed control technique that can be applied in all situations. The integrated weed-management method encourages the blending of several weed-control strategies in order to provide effective, long-lasting, cost-effective and environmentally friendly weed management. Therefore, the development of integrated weed-management techniques should be preceded.

Figure 2: Mechanised land levelling using tractor-drawn planer

3.2. Biological Weed Management

Introducing a biocontrol agent is a low cost and efficient way to manage weeds because of the self-sustaining behaviour of these organisms. These biological pest controllers have been modified so that they only consume the intended plant (Table 5) (Mahajan et al., 2012; Medd et al., 2001). Climate change alters the interactions between invasive plants, herbivorous insects and native plants, reducing the effectiveness of biological control and having unintended consequences for native species. Most bio-control mechanisms function best in a stable environment. Changes in the response of the host plant to high CO₂, drought, or flooding affect the fitness, phenology and geographic ranges of plants and insects, which affects the non-target effects of invasive biocontrol insects on native species and ecosystems (Lu et al., 2015; Gerard 2010). For example, Environmental Niche Modelling (ENM) for *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* and its agent reveal that a large portion of the introduced agents are expected to

fail when mean annual temperature and rainfall rise (Simberloff, 2012). Bio-agent abundance is reduced by 21.6% as a result of CO₂-induced changes in plant chemistry and herbivore performance (Amare, 2016). Direct effects of CO₂ on raising starch concentration in leaves and decreasing nitrogen content also have an impact on biocontrol through affecting herbivore behaviour and development rate (Naidu, 2015). Climate change also impacts the global distribution of weeds and bio-control agents. For example, increase in temperature permits subtropical biological control agents to persist on weeds more in temperate environments thus less effective in subtropical region. *Salvinia molesta* and *Alternanthera philoxeroides* are two aquatic weeds that may be preferred in southern areas, but a recent study found that these weeds are spreading northward (Madafiglio, 2000). Thus, biological control programs for these weeds have often limited as the biocontrol agent is more effective in their region (Simberloff, 2012). As a result of increased water stress or drought, some weed species may have higher levels of various insect-resistance and allelochemicals (Gerard et al., 2010). In drier environments, the effectiveness of biocontrol may be reduced because water stress affects the development of both host plants and bio-agents.

Table 5. Some common biological control agents reported from different countries

Weeds	Bio-agent	Reporting country	Kinds of bioagent
<i>Chondrilla juncea</i>	<i>Puccinia chondrillina</i>	Australia	Plant pathogen
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	<i>Bactra verutana</i>	India, USA	Shoot boring moth
<i>Echinochloa spp.</i>	<i>Emmalocera spp.</i>	India	Stem boring moth
<i>Hydrilla verticillata</i>	<i>Hydrellia pakistanae</i>	USA	Shoot fly
<i>Orobanche cernua</i>	<i>Sclerotinia sp.</i>	USA	Plant pathogen
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>	<i>Zygogramma bicolorata</i> <i>Epiblema strenuana</i> <i>Contrachelus sp.</i>	India Australia	Leaf eating beetle, Stem galling insect and Stem galling insect
<i>Rumex spp.</i>	<i>Uromyces rumicis</i> <i>Gastrophysa viridula</i>	USA	Plant pathogen Beetle
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	<i>Microlarinus lareynii</i> and <i>M. lypriformi</i>	USA	Pod weevil

3.3. Chemical Weed Management

Herbicide coverage, persistence, mode of action, efficacy and selectivity may be influenced by temperature, CO₂, soil moisture, wind speed and other climatic conditions. Herbicide efficacy in sensitive plants is influenced by a number of factors, including herbicide absorption and translocation, herbicide metabolism and herbicide binding to the target site (Bailey, 2004; Devine et al., 1993). Environmental factors at the plant level may have an impact on these variables (microclimate). Weed resistance to herbicides, on the other hand, is likely to rise due to more aggressive weed growth under future climate conditions, potentially reducing the efficacy of commonly used herbicides (Staubaut and Dejonckheere, 1997; Rosenzweig et al., 2001). Thus, significant effect of climate change on herbicide efficacy must be closely examined.

3.3.1. Effect of Elevated CO₂ Level on Herbicide Efficacy, Translocation and Other Factors

Elevated CO₂ levels in atmosphere are anticipated to have a significant impact on herbicide efficacy on weeds by diluting the foliar-applied herbicides absorbed in plants, especially in C₃ weeds than C₄ weeds (reducing the herbicide concentration that binds to the target site of C₃

weeds) (Knapp et al., 1993; Holland and Sinclair, 2004). For example, as shown in the Table 6, *Chenopodium album* is a C₃ weed with stronger resistance to Glyphosate due to increased growth and biomass at elevated CO₂ than any C₄ weed (*Chloris gayana*, *Eragrostis curvula* and *Paspalum dilatatum*) (Maneet al., 2011).

Table 6: Effects of increased CO₂ concentration on glyphosate efficacy for various weed species with different photosynthetic pathways

Common name	Scientific name	Photosynthetic pathway	Efficacy change
Canada thistle	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	C ₃	Reduced
Dallis grass	<i>Paspalum dilatatum</i>	C ₄	None
Lambsquarters	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	C ₃	Reduced
Lovegrass	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	C ₄	None
Quackgrass	<i>Elytrigia repens</i>	C ₃	Reduced
Redroot pigweed	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	C ₄	None
Rhodes grass	<i>Chloris gayana</i>	C ₄	None
Smut grass	<i>Sporobolus indicus</i>	C ₄	None

Perennial weeds will grow more frequently as CO₂ levels rise due to improved photosynthesis, making herbicide control more difficult (Blumenthal et al., 2008). It is found that field-grown Canada thistle (*Cirsium arvense*) grow more vigorously and rapidly due to higher root-to-shoot ratio and diluting effect on glyphosate effectiveness at the below-ground development had a (Ziska, 2004). Elevated CO₂ levels might increase leaf cuticular thickness, decrease stomatal number and decrease conductance, thereby restricting herbicide uptake. For example, plants exposed to high CO₂ concentrations (720 ppm) are more tolerant to glyphosate than plants subjected to ambient CO₂ concentrations of 380 ppm (Jugulam et al., 2018). Efficacy of the linuron was reduced by 15% in wild buckwheat (*Polygonum convolvulus*) at double-ambient CO₂ levels due to its direct impact on photosynthetic activity at elevated CO₂ concentrations and its pronounced effect on the efficacy of herbicide chemistries such as Photosystem II inhibitors (PSII) and pigment inhibitors that interfere with photosynthesis.

3.3.2. Effect of Increased Temperature Level on Herbicide Efficacy, Translocation and Other Factors

Temperature has a direct impact on the rate of herbicide diffusion, the viscosity of cuticle waxes and the physicochemical properties of the spray solution, all of which can have an immediate effect on herbicide performance. Due to climate change, higher temperature has been demonstrated to reduce the viscosity of cuticular lipids, improving herbicide permeability and diffusion through the cuticle (Price, 1983; Fausey and Renner, 2001). Flumiclorac showed higher activity on *Chenopodium album* (7x) and *Amaranthus retroflexus* (3x) as the temperature increased from 10 °C to 40 °C (Figure 3) (Fausey and Renner, 2001). Prolong high temperatures impair the efficacy and selectivity of pre- and post-emergence herbicides. Pre emergence herbicide efficacy is reduced due to variable rainfall before crop sowing and post emergence herbicide efficacy is reduced due to higher plant growth rates at high temperatures results in narrower the herbicide spraying window of crop-weed competition. Increasing temperature and metabolic activity increased the absorption and translocation of several herbicides, resulting in better efficacy of selected herbicides (Patterson et al., 1999).

Figure 3: Effect of temperature on activity of flumiclorac 72 h after treatment

For example, glyphosate translocation is higher to the meristematic tissues of soybean at 35°C than at 15°C, probably due to increased herbicide movements at higher temperatures (Pline et al., 1999). High temperatures, on the other hand, may improve root uptake of herbicides in some situations because of loss in soil organic matter and high transpiration rates. On the other hand, high temperatures cause temporary herbicide molecules to degrade quickly, aiding in the detoxification of reactive oxygen molecules and reducing herbicide activity on target plants (Kells et al., 1984). For example, when *Amaranthus palmeri* plants were subjected to high temperatures, the efficacy of Mesotrione (an HPPD inhibitor) is reduced by 6 to 7 times due to detoxification of reactive oxygen molecules (Godar et al., 2015). The high temperature had a significant impact on herbicide (pre-emergence, such as Fluchloralin) volatilization from soils. Triallate also follow the same trends and losses in soil increase from 14% to 60% (Atienza et al., 2001). Higher temperatures cause plant tissues to contain less protein, reducing the need for aromatic and branched-chain amino acids and decreasing the effectiveness of herbicides that inhibit enzymes, such as glyphosate (N-phosphonomethyl glycine) (Varanasi et al., 2016). So, the effect of temperature on herbicide follows the variable trends in climate change.

3.3.3. Effect of Variable Rainfall on Herbicide Efficacy, Translocation and Other Factors

Herbicide efficacy varies with rainfall timing and intensity and variations in precipitation patterns may favour herbicide dissipation rather than persistence. Precipitation and relative humidity (RH) are important climatic factors influencing herbicide retention on the leaf surface, as well as absorption and translocation within the plant (Stenrod et al., 2008; Clements et al., 2014). As a result of climate change, the water cycle is becoming more intense. This will result in more intense droughts and extreme rainstorms, as well as more flooding. In contrast to the subtropics, precipitation is predicted to decrease in the high latitudes (Usman et al., 2019). Changes to monsoon precipitation are expected, which will vary by region and rain shower occurs during the rain-fast period reduced the effectiveness of herbicides or increases the crop injury. "Rain-fastness" refers to the amount of time that must elapse after the application of a herbicide without any rain (Table 7). Herbicides with lipophilic characteristics are frequently more rain-fast than water-soluble herbicides (Kudsk et al., 1990). Variable rainfall affects the rain-fastness of the herbicides thus reducing the herbicide efficacy. For example, pendimethalin

required 2 hours of rain less to be effective in controlling weeds (Duary and Jaiswal, 2021). Herbicide efficacy decreases because of drought-related effects like reduced stomatal aperture, thickening of the cuticle and increased leaf pubescence. For example, *Urochloa Plantagenet* grown under water stress condition and the activity of Acetyl CoA Carboxylase (ACCase) inhibitors was much decreased due to water stress related issue (Pereira, 2010). Plant roots, on the other hand, cannot absorb pre-emergence herbicides in dry conditions. They won't be able to reach their target if the soil is too dry. This allows them to adsorb in soil particles and heavy rains immediately following application may result in herbicide loss due to leaching (Soukup et al., 2004). Moisture stress may increase herbicide persistence due to slower microbial breakdown in soil (Arıkan et al., 2015) thus, under the moisture stress, more application rates or the use of specific surfactants may be required to improve herbicide performance.

Table 7. Rain-fastness of different herbicides

Herbicides	Hours until rain-fast
2,4-D Amine	6–8
2,4-D Ester	1
Atrazine	1–2*
<i>Pinoxaden</i>	0.5
Glyphosate	1-6**
Paraquat	0.5
Tembotrione	1
Glufosinate-ammonium	4
Imazethapyr	1
Sulfosulfuron	2
Mesosulfuron	4
Metsulfuron	6
Dicamba	4
Bispyribac sodium	4-6
Cyhalofop- butyl	2
Pemoxulam	1-2
Quizalofop-ethyl	1

* Rainfall will improve control from root uptake.

** Rain can reduce the effectiveness of an application within 6 hours. Heavy rain within 2 hours of application may wash the chemical off the foliage, requiring another treatment.

Relative humidity may have a greater influence on the uptake of foliar-applied herbicides than temperature. High humidity, on the other hand, reduces the effects of high temperature on drying of droplet due to longer leaf retention time; hence, greater herbicide absorption. The efficiency of Glufosinate ammonium on green foxtail and barley was better when the humidity was high (Anderson et al., 1993). It is investigated the efficiency of Glufpsinate ammonium on wild oat plants cultivated at high (>95%) and low (40%) relative humidity. Glufpsinate ammonium uptake and efficacy increased dramatically in plants exposed to high RH for 30 minutes before and after herbicide treatment compared to those left at low RH continuously (Ramsey et al., 2002). Cuticle hydration and stomatal opening increase in high humidity, enhancing the penetration of water-soluble herbicides into the leaf surface (Kudsk et al., 1990). Most herbicides were shown to have better uptake and efficacy when plants were subjected to

high humidity after spraying, implying that delayed droplet drying, rather than cuticle hydration, could be the cause for higher efficacy at high humidity levels.

3.3.4. Effect of Climate Change on Herbicide Resistance

When herbicides are applied repeatedly over several seasons, susceptible plants of a weed species fall dramatically, but resistant biotypes gradually grow to the point that the herbicide appears to be ineffective (Duary, 2008). Climate change is also increasing to herbicide resistance, notably in C3 weeds, which are more sensitive to CO₂ enhancement. For example, reduced efficiency in *Cirsium arvense* (C3) due to dilution and higher root biomass in a CO₂ enriched environment (Ziska et al., 2004). Herbicide resistance typically results from a single (or multiple) resistant gene that is naturally present in any one individual in a large population over a large area (Duary, 2008). Climate change affect gene flow and transfer of gene between resistant crop and related weed species, depending on genetic similarities (Ziska, 2019). A long-term study demonstrated that increased CO₂ levels (300, 400 and 600 ppm) cause better synchrony in blooming periods and increased outcrossing rates between cultivated rice and *Oryza sativa f. spontaneacultivar* (StgS) (Anwar, 2021). As a result, as CO₂ levels increased, the number of weedy herbicide-resistant hybrid progeny also increased (Ziska et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2011). Temperature fluctuations in plants had a significant impact on the range of herbicide sensitivity. For example, *Lolium spp.* have a varied positive response to ACCase inhibitors at normal temperatures, but their activity decreases as temperatures rise (Matzrafi et al., 2016). Another study concluded that pinoxaden absorption was lower at high temperatures than at low temperatures, most likely due to temperature-dependent uptake as well as abiotic and enzymatic hydrolytic activities (Fantke et al., Cirillo 2014). Variations in the average temperature and CO₂ concentration will increase the resistance mechanism in the near future thus there is an urgent need of integrated weed management.

3.3.5. Effect of Sea Level Induced Salinity on Herbicide Efficacy, Translocation and Other Factors

Atmospheric CO₂ increases plant biomass and leaf area, which may be offset by increased salinity thus herbicide efficacy is unchanged. However, foliar adsorption may decrease as a result of salinity-induced anatomical/physiological changes (increased leaf thickness, wax production and stomatal closure) (Cirillo et al., 2018). Atrazine adsorption was increased while desorption was inhibited by sodium ions. This could have a major impact on herbicide persistence in soil, relative control efficacy and overall environmental impact. Sacala et al. (2008) discovered a significant interaction between glufosinate sprays and NaCl stress in maize under hydroponic culture, resulting in a significant decrease in leaf ammonium concentration as compared to the application of just one herbicide. Considering that the phytotoxicity of Glufosinate is due to ammonium accumulation, there may be an antagonism between salinity and Glufosinate (Sacala et al., 2008). Furthermore, soil salinization reduces microbial activity. Lactofen (and its metabolite desethyl lactofen) and acifluorfen breakdown rates, for example, were slower in salty soils due to the inhibitory effects of salt on soil microorganisms (Jing et al., 2018). Lower herbicide persistence linked to global warming may result in diminished herbicide efficacy since weed and crop establishment are both delayed in saline soils. As a result, herbicide applications will need to be rescheduled to coincide with crop emergence dates or employed as early post-emergence treatments.

4. Conclusion and Future Research

Considering all the studies on the impact of climate change on weed-crop interactions, conclusions may be drawn that weeds are more intelligent than cultivated crops and can adapt to climate change more quickly. Weeds have more adaptive power in changing situation thus more competitive over crop. Apart from climate change, edaphic variables and crop

management methods, such as the use of new herbicide classes, are expected to influence weed distribution, translocation and shift. Due to the complexity of the interaction between climate, soil, crops and weeds, considerable research covering wide range of cropping systems under different climatic and edaphic environments is required to develop long-term weed management techniques, improve resilience and provide realistic solution of the climate change problem.

5. Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare. All co-authors have seen and agree with the contents of the manuscript and there is no financial interest to report. We certify that the submission is original work and is not under review at any other publication.

6. Author contribution

B.D. and U.D. contributed to the design and implementation of the article and to the writing of the manuscript.

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The data that support this study are available in the article and accompanying online supplementary material.

9. References

- Adkins S, Shabbir A. Biology, ecology and management of the invasive parthenium weed (*Parthenium hysterophorus* L.). *Pest management science*. 2014; 70(7):1023-9.
- Aggarwal D, Pasricha JS. Climate Change and its Impacts on Indian Agriculture. *International Journal of Climate Change: Impacts & Responses*. 2011; 2(3).
- Alberto AM, Ziska LH, Cervancia CR, Manalo PA. The influence of increasing carbon dioxide and temperature on competitive interactions between a C3 crop, rice (*Oryza sativa*) and a C4 weed (*Echinochloa glabrescens*). *Functional Plant Biology*. 1996;23(6):795-802.
- Amare T. Review on impact of climate change on weed and their management. *American Journal of Biological and Environmental Statistics*. 2016;2(3):21-7.
- Anderson DM, Swanton CJ, Hall JC, Mersey BG. The influence of temperature and relative humidity on the efficacy of Glufosinate-ammonium. *Weed Research*. 1993; 33(2):13947.
- Anon, 2004. Weed result index blackberry. *Weed Control Manual for the Bay of Plenty*. <http://www.envbop.govt.nz/weeds/weed26.asp>.
- Anwar MP, Islam AM, Yeasmin S, Rashid MH, Juraimi AS, Ahmed S, Shrestha A. Weeds and Their Responses to Management Efforts in A Changing Climate. *Agronomy*. 2021; 11(10):1921.
- Arıkan N, Burçak A.A, Türkteşmel I, Akba,SA. Persistence of herbicide in soil. *Turk. J. Occup. /Environ. Med. Saf*. 2015, 1;1.
- Atienza J, Tabernero MT, Álvarez-Benedí J, Sanz M. Volatilisation of triallate as affected by soil texture and air velocity. *Chemosphere*. 2001; 42(3):257-61.
- B. Duary and D. K. Jaiswal. Impact of rain on efficacy of pendimethalin in dry DSR, *Experiment Findings, ISWS newsletter*. 2021; 4-5.
- Bailey SW. Climate change and decreasing herbicide persistence. *Pest Management Science: formerly Pesticide Science*. 2004; 60(2):158-62.
- Bailey-Serres J, Voeselek LA. Flooding stress: acclimations and genetic diversity. *Annual review of plant biology*. 2008; 59:313.

- Bajwa AA, Wang H, Chauhan BS, Adkins SW. Effect of elevated carbon dioxide concentration on growth, productivity, and glyphosate response of parthenium weed (*Parthenium hysterophorus* L.). *Pest management science*. 2019; 75(11):2934-41.
- Bhowmik PC, Reddy KN. Effects of barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) on growth, yield, and nutrient status of transplanted tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*). *Weed Science*. 1988; 36(6):775-8.
- Blumenthal D, Chimner RA, Welker JM, Morgan JA. Increased snow facilitates plant invasion in mixedgrass prairie. *New Phytologist*. 2008; 179(2):440-8.
- Boote KJ, Allen LH, Prasad PV, Baker JT, Gesch RW, Snyder AM, Pan D, Thomas JM. Elevated temperature and CO₂ impacts on pollination, reproductive growth, and yield of several globally important crops. *Journal of Agricultural Meteorology*. 2005; 60(5):469-74.
- Borsai O, Hassan MA, Negruşier C, Raigón MD, Boscaiu M, Sestraş RE, Vicente O. Responses to salt stress in *Portulaca*: Insight into its tolerance mechanisms. *Plants*. 2020; 9(12):1660.
- Ottis BV, Smith KL, Scott RC, Talbert RE. Rice yield and quality as affected by cultivar and red rice (*Oryza sativa*) density. *Weed Science*. 2005; 53(4):499-504.
- Carlson RW, Bazzaz FA. The effects of elevated CO₂ concentrations on growth, photosynthesis, transpiration, and water use efficiency of plants. In *Environmental and climatic impact of coal utilization. Proceedings of a Symposium, Williamsburg, Virginia, USA, April 17-19, 1979*. Singh, JJ; Deepak, A.(Editors). 1980 (pp. 609-623). Academic Press.
- Carter DR, Peterson KM. Effects of a CO₂-enriched atmosphere on the growth and competitive interaction of a C₃ and a C₄ grass. *Oecologia*. 1983; 58(2):188-93.
- Chandrasena N. How will weed management change under climate change? Some perspectives. *Journal of Crop and Weed*. 2009; 5(2):95-105.
- Chauhan BS, Johnson DE. Growth and reproduction of junglerice (*Echinochloa colona*) in response to water stress. *Weed Science*. 2010; 58(2):132-5.
- Cirillo V, Masin R, Maggio A, Zanin G. Crop-weed interactions in saline environments. *European Journal of Agronomy*. 2018; 99:51-61.
- Clements DR, DiTommaso A, Hyvönen T. Ecology and management of weeds in a changing climate. In *Recent advances in weed management 2014* (pp. 13-37). Springer, New York, NY.
- Coumou D, Rahmstorf S (2012) A decade of weather extremes. *Nat Clim Chang* 2:491–496.
- Kriticos D, Crossman ND, Ota N, Scott JK. Climate change and invasive plants in South Australia. Canberra, Australia: CSIRO Climate Adaptation Flagship; 2010 May 3.
- Das TK. Resource Conserving Techniques and Weed Control Efficiency. *Resource Conserving Techniques in Crop Production*. 2011; 367.
- Dekker J. The foxtail (*Setaria*) species-group. *Weed science*. 2003 Oct;51(5):641-56.
- Devine, M.D., Duke, S.O., and Fedtke, C. (1993) *Foliar Absorption of Herbicides*. PrenticeHall, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey.
- Duary B. Recent advances in herbicide resistance in weeds and its management. *Indian J. Weed Sci*. 2008; 24:124-35.
- Dukes JS, Mooney HA. Does global change increase the success of biological invaders?. *Trends in ecology & evolution*. 1999; 14(4):135-9.
- Eom SH, DiTommaso A, Weston LA. Effects of soil salinity in the growth of *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* biotypes collected from roadside and agricultural field. *Journal of plant nutrition*. 2013 Dec 6;36(14):2191-204.

- Fantke P, Gillespie BW, Juraske R, Jolliet O. Estimating half-lives for pesticide dissipation from plants. *Environmental science & technology*. 2014 Aug 5;48(15):8588-602.
- Fausey JC, Renner KA. Environmental effects on CGA-248757 and flumiclorac efficacy/soybean tolerance. *Weed Science*. 2001 Oct;49(5):668-74.
- Fleming A, Vanclay F. Farmer responses to climate change and sustainable agriculture. A review. *Agronomy for sustainable development*. 2010 Mar;30(1):11-9.
- Fuentes RG, Baltazar AM, Merca FE, Ismail AM, Johnson DE. Morphological and physiological responses of lowland purple nutsedge (*Cyperus rotundus* L.) to flooding. *AoB plants*. 2010 Jan 1;2010.
- Gerard PJ, Kean JM, Phillips CB, Fowler SV, Withers TM, Walker GP, Charles JG. Possible impacts of climate change on biocontrol systems in New Zealand. Report for MAF Pol Project. 2010 Sep 2:0910-11689.
- Giannini A, Biasutti M, Held IM, Sobel AH. A global perspective on African climate. *Climatic Change*. 2008 Oct;90(4):359-83.
- Gillham SW, Summerton MJ. A water utility's approach to addressing the potential impacts of climate change. In *Climate Change Adaptation in the Water Sector 2012* May 4 (pp. 199-208). Routledge.
- Godar AS, Varanasi VK, Nakka S, Prasad PV, Thompson CR, Mithila J. Physiological and molecular mechanisms of differential sensitivity of Palmer amaranth (*Amaranthus palmeri*) to mesotrione at varying growth temperatures. *PloS one*. 2015 May 19;10(5):e0126731.
- Hayman P, Sadras V. Climate change and weed management in Australian farming systems. In *15th Australian Weeds Conference, Adelaide, South Australia* (eds C. Preston, JH Watts & ND Crossman) 2006 Sep (pp. 22-26).
- Hobbs PR, Gupta RK. Resource-Conserving Technologies for Wheat in the Rice–Wheat System. *Improving the Productivity and Sustainability of Rice-Wheat Systems: Issues and Impacts*. 2003 Jan 1; 65:149-71.
- Holland J, Sinclair P. Environmental fate of pesticides and the consequences for residues in food and drinking water. *Pesticide residues in food and drinking water: Human exposure and risks*. 2003 Oct 31:27-62.
- Holm L, Doll J, Holm E, Pancho JV, Herberger JP. *World weeds: natural histories and distribution*. John Wiley & Sons; 1997; 4(7): 203-305.
- Houghton E. *Climate change 1995: The science of climate change: contribution of working group I to the second assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. 1996; 4(6): 405-490.
- Hussain MI, Shackleton R, El-Keblawy A, González L, Trigo M. Impact of the invasive *Prosopis juliflora* on terrestrial ecosystems. *Sustainable Agriculture Reviews* 52. 2021:223-78.
- Hussein SA. *Mechanisms of salt tolerance in the halophytes *Atriplex nummularia* Lind. and *Atriplex leucoclada* Boiss* (Doctoral dissertation, Hannover: Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover). 2007: 20-67.
- Change IC. Impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability. Part A: global and sectoral aspects. Contribution of working group II to the fifth assessment report of the intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. 2014 Mar; 1132. IPCC, 2004. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC Fourth Assessment Report: Climate Change 2007 (AR4). <http://www.ipcc.ch>

- Jaganathan GK, Liu B. Role of seed sowing time and microclimate on germination and seedling establishment of *Dodonaea viscosa* (Sapindaceae) in a seasonal dry tropical environment—an insight into restoration efforts. *Botany*. 2015;93(1):23-9.
- Jamshidi K, Yousefi AR, Oveisi M. Effect of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) intercropping on weed biomass and maize (*Zea mays*) yield. *New Zealand Journal of Crop and Horticultural Science*. 2013 Dec 1;41(4):180-8.
- Jamshidizadeh A, Farzaneh M, Nasernakhaei F. Germination and Some Morphophysiological Traits of *Convolvulus arvensis* in Response to Salinity Stress. *Iranian Journal of Seed Research*. 2021 Mar 10;7(2):89-106.
- Jat ML, Chandna P, Gupta R, Sharma SK, Gill MA. Laser land leveling: A precursor technology for resource conservation. *Rice-Wheat consortium technical bulletin series*. 2006; 7:48.
- Jing X, Yang J, Wang T. Effects of salinity on herbicide lactofen residues in soil. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*. 2018 Jan;229(1):1-7.
- Joos F, Prentice IC, Sitch S, Meyer R, Hooss G, Plattner GK, Gerber S, Hasselmann K. Global warming feedbacks on terrestrial carbon uptake under the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) emission scenarios. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*. 2001 Dec;15(4):891-907.
- Jugulam M, Varanasi AK, Varanasi VK, Prasad PV. Climate change influence on herbicide efficacy and weed management. *Food Security and Climate Change*. 2018 Nov 19:43348.
- Kells JJ, Meggitt WF, Penner D. Absorption, translocation, and activity of fluzifop-butyl as influenced by plant growth stage and environment. *Weed Science*. 1984 Mar;32(2):143-9.
- Khan SA, Kumar S, Hussain MZ, Kalra N. Climate change, climate variability and Indian agriculture: impacts vulnerability and adaptation strategies. In *Climate change and crops 2009* (pp. 19-38). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Knapp AK, Hamerlynck EP, Owensby CE. Photosynthetic and water relations responses to elevated CO₂ in the C₄ grass *Andropogon gerardii*. *International Journal of Plant Sciences*. 1993 Dec 1;154(4):459-66.
- Korres NE, Norsworthy JK, Tehranchian P, Gitsopoulos TK, Loka DA, Oosterhuis DM, Gealy DR, Moss SR, Burgos NR, Miller MR, Palhano M. Cultivars to face climate change effects on crops and weeds: a review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*. 2016 Mar;36(1):1-22.
- Kriticos DJ, Sutherst RW, Brown JR, Adkins SW, Maywald GF. Climate change and biotic invasions: a case history of a tropical woody vine. *Biological Invasions*. 2003 Sep;5(3):147-65.
- Kriticos D, Crossman ND, Ota N, Scott JK. Climate change and invasive plants in South Australia. Canberra, Australia: CSIRO Climate Adaptation Flagship. 2010; 9(6): 20049.
- Kudsk P, Olesen T, Thonke KE. The influence of temperature, humidity and simulated rain on the performance of thiameturon-methyl. *Weed Research*. 1990 Aug;30(4):261-9.
- Laffan SW. Assessing regional scale weed distributions, with an Australian example using *Nassella trichotoma*. *Weed Research*. 2006 Jun;46(3):194-206.
- Lee JS. Combined effect of elevated CO₂ and temperature on the growth and phenology of two annual C₃ and C₄ weedy species. *Agriculture, ecosystems & environment*. 2011 Mar 1;140(3-4):484-91.

- Lu X, Siemann E, He M, Wei H, Shao X, Ding J. Climate warming increases biological control agent impact on a non-target species. *Ecology letters*. 2015 Jan;18(1):48-56.
- De Ven V. Temperature-mediated responses of flumetsulam and metosulam on *Raphanus raphanistrum*. *Weed Research*. 2000 Aug;40(4):387-95.
- Mahajan G, Singh S, Chauhan BS. Impact of climate change on weeds in the rice-wheat cropping system. *Current science*. 2012 May 1;102(9):1254-5.
- Malarkodi N, Manikandan N, Ramaraj AP. Impact of climate change on weeds and weed management—A review. *Journal of Innovative Agriculture*. 2017; 4:1-6.
- Mandal AK, Dheebakaran G, Banik M, Kumar A, Prasad SA. Response of Bermuda grass (*Cynodon dactylon*) growth under elevated temperature and moisture stress condition. *Pharma Innov J [Internet]*. 2017;6(12):83-7.
- Manea A, Leishman MR, Downey PO. Exotic C4 grasses have increased tolerance to glyphosate under elevated carbon dioxide. *Weed Science*. 2011 Mar;59(1):28-36.
- Mary J. Weeds and their Management under Changing Climate: A Review. *Agricultural Reviews*. 2021 Sep 1;42(3).
- Matloob A, Khaliq A, Chauhan BS. Weeds of direct-seeded rice in Asia: problems and opportunities. *Advances in agronomy*. 2015 Jan 1; 130:291-336.
- Matzrafi M, Seiwert B, Reemtsma T, Rubin B, Peleg Z. Climate change increases the risk of herbicide-resistant weeds due to enhanced detoxification. *Planta*. 2016 Dec;244(6):1217-27.
- Medd RW, Van De Ven RJ, Pickering DI, Nordblom T. Determination of environment-specific dose–response relationships for clodinafop-propargyl on *Avena* spp. *Weed Research*. 2001 Aug 18;41(4):351-68.
- Mehwish N. *Adaptive Component for salinity tolerance in Cyperus laevigatus L. populations from diverse salt-affected habitats* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad.). Mishra, G. N. 2003. Weeds and their management in upland rice. *Indian Farming (August)*: 18-21.
- Mooney H.A, and Hobbs R. J. *Invasive Species in a Changing World*. Washington, DC: Island Press. 2000; 4(5): 4-57.
- Naidu VS. Climate change, crop-weed balance and the future of weed management.
- Naidu VS, Varshney JA. Interactive effect of elevated CO₂. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. 2011 Nov;81(11):1026-9.
- Nichols V, Verhulst N, Cox R, Govaerts B. Weed dynamics and conservation agriculture principles: A review. *Field Crops Research*. 2015 Nov 1; 183:56-68.
- Nitze WA, Topping JC, Goldberg M, Devic M, Schultz E. Reducing our food's impact on climate change. *Clim. Alert*. 2008;18(6).
- Patterson DT. Responses of soybean (*Glycine max*) and three C4 grass weeds to CO₂ enrichment during drought. *Weed Science*. 1986 Mar;34(2):203-10.
- Patterson DT. Weeds in a changing climate. *Weed Science*. 1995 Dec;43(4):685-700.
- Patterson DT, Westbrook JK, Lingren PD, Rogasik J. Weeds, insects, and diseases. *Climatic change*. 1999 Dec;43(4):711-27.
- Patterson DT, Flint EP. Potential effects of global atmospheric CO₂ enrichment on the growth and competitiveness of C3 and C4 weed and crop plants. *Weed Science*. 1980 Jan;28(1):71-5.
- Patterson DT, Westbrook JK, Lingren PD, Rogasik J. Weeds, insects, and diseases. *Climatic change*. 1999 Dec;43(4):711-27.

- Pereira MR, Martins D, Silva JI, Rodrigues-Costa AC, Klar AE. Efeito de herbicidas sobre plantas de *Brachiaria plantaginea* submetidas a estresse hídrico. *Planta Daninha*. 2010; 28:1047-58.
- Peters K, Breitsameter L, Gerowitt B. Impact of climate change on weeds in agriculture: a review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*. 2014 Oct;34(4):707-21.
- Pline WA, Wu J, Hatzios KK. Effects of temperature and chemical additives on the response of transgenic herbicide-resistant soybeans to glufosinate and glyphosate applications. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*. 1999 Oct 1;65(2):119-31.
- Poorter H. Interspecific variation in the growth response of plants to an elevated ambient CO₂ concentration. In *CO₂ and Biosphere 1993* (pp. 77-98). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Poorter H, Navas ML. Plant growth and competition at elevated CO₂: on winners, losers and functional groups. *New Phytologist*. 2003 Feb;157(2):175-98.
- Price CE. The effect of environment on foliage uptake and translocation of herbicides. *Aspects of applied biology*. 1983;4(1983):157-69.
- Ramesh K, Matloob A, Aslam F, Florentine SK, Chauhan BS. Weeds in a changing climate: vulnerabilities, consequences, and implications for future weed management. *Frontiers in plant science*. 2017 Feb 13; 8:95.
- Ramsey RJ, Stephenson GR, Hall JC. Effect of relative humidity on the uptake, translocation, and efficacy of glufosinate ammonium in wild oat (*Avena fatua*). *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*. 2002 May 1;73(1):1-8.
- Rana SS, Rana MC. Principles, and practices of weed management. Department of Agronomy, College of Agriculture, CSK Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya, Palampur. 2016;138.
- Rao AN, Johnson DE, Sivaprasad B, Ladha JK, Mortimer AM. Weed management in directseeded rice. *Advances in agronomy*. 2007 Jan 1; 93:153-255.
- Rengel Z. Soil pH, soil health and climate change. In *Soil health and climate change 2011* (pp. 69-85). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Rodenburg J, Meinke H, Johnson DE. Challenges for weed management in African rice systems in a changing climate. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*. 2011 Aug;149(4):427-35.
- Rosenzweig C, Iglesias A, Yang XB, Epstein PR, Chivian E. Climate change and extreme weather events-Implications for food production, plant diseases, and pests.
- Sacała E, Podgórska-Lesiak M, Demczuk A. Glufosinate phytotoxicity to maize under salt stress conditions. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*. 2008 Nov 1;17(6):993-6.
- Sakai AK, Allendorf FW, Holt JS, Lodge DM, Molofsky J, With KA, Baughman S, Cabin RJ, Cohen JE, Ellstrand NC, McCauley DE. The population biology of invasive species. *Annual review of ecology and systematics*. 2001 Jan 1:305-32.
- Sarathambal C, Rathore M, Jaggi D, Kumar B. Response of soil enzymes to elevated CO₂ and temperature in weeds associated with rice-wheat cropping system. *Indian Journal of Weed Science*. 2016; 48(1): 29-32.
- Simberloff D. Risks of biological control for conservation purposes. *BioControl*. 2012 Apr;57(2):263-76.
- Singer BD, Ziska LH, Frenz DA, Gebhard DE, Straka JG. Increasing ambient CO₂ content in common ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*) pollen as a function of rising atmospheric CO₂ concentration. *Functional Plant Biology*. 2005 Jul 7;32(7):667-70.
- Singh MC, Dubey SC, Yaduraju NT. Climate change and its possible impacts on weeds. *International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology*. 2016;5(3):1530-9.

- Singh RP, Singh RK, Singh MK. Impact of climate and carbon dioxide change on weeds and their management-a review. *Indian Journal of Weed Science*. 2011;43(1&2):1-1.
- Soukup J, Jursík M, Hamouz P, Holec J, Krupka J. Influence of soil pH, rainfall, dosage, and application timing of herbicide Merlin 750 WG (isoxaflutole) on phytotoxicity level in maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Plant Soil and Environment*. 2004 Feb 1;50(2):88-94.
- Stenrød M, Perceval J, Benoit P, Almvik M, Bolli RI, Eklo OM, Sveistrup TE, Kværner J. Cold climatic conditions: Effects on bioavailability and leaching of the mobile pesticide metribuzin in a silt loam soil in Norway. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*. 2008 Jun 1;53(1):4-15.
- Steurbaut W, Dejonckheere W. Neveneffecten van pesticiden. *Problemen van de Arbeidsgeneeskunde*. 1997; 32:311-26.
- Stitt M. Rising CO₂ levels and their potential significance for carbon flow in photosynthetic cells. *Plant, Cell & Environment*. 1991 Oct;14(8):741-62.
- Tanveer M, & Shah A.N. An insight into salt stress tolerance mechanisms of *Chenopodium album*. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2017; 24(19): 16531-16535.
- Tubiello FN, Soussana J-F, Howden SM. Crop and pasture response to climate change. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 2007; 104:19686–19690.
- Udayashankara TH, Murthy BS, Madhukar M. Impact of climate change on rainfall pattern and reservoir level. *Journal of Water Resource Engineering and Management*. 2016;3(1):10-4.
- Ullah A, Bano A, Khan N. Climate change and salinity effects on crops and chemical communication between plants and plant growth-promoting microorganisms under stress. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*. 2021:161.
- UN. United Nations Population Estimates. 2019. Available online: <https://www.un.org/development/desa/en/news/population/world-populationprospects-2019.html> (accessed on 13 November 2020).
- Upasani RR, Barla S. Weed dynamics in changing climate. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. Appl. Sci*. 2018; 66:3435-50.
- Usman, M., Ahmad, B. and Bukhari, S.A.A., 2019. Assessment of inter-seasonal, inter-annual and intra-annual variability in snow and rainfall recharged freshwater discharge under IPCC AR5 based climate change scenarios: a case study of Soan river basin, Potowar region, Pakistan. *Climate Change*, 5(20), pp.264-326.
- Varanasi A, Prasad PV, Jugulam M. Impact of climate change factors on weeds and herbicide efficacy. *Advances in agronomy*. 2016 Jan 1;135:107-46.
- Varanasi A, Prasad PV, Jugulam M. Impact of climate change factors on weeds and herbicide efficacy. *Advances in agronomy*. 2016 Jan 1;135:107-46.
- Walck JL, Hidayati SN, Dixon KW, Thompson KE, Poschlod P. Climate change and plant regeneration from seed. *Global Change Biology*. 2011 Jun;17(6):2145-61.
- Walther GR, Post E, Convey P, Menzel A, Parmesan C, Beebee TJ, Fromentin JM, HoeghGuldberg O, Bairlein F. Ecological responses to recent climate change. *Nature*. 2002 Mar;416(6879):389-95.
- Waterhouse DF. Biological control of weeds: Southeast Asian prospects. 1994; 2(3): 30-90.
- Wilson RG, Kerr ED, Nelson LA. Potential for using weed seed content in the soil to predict future weed problems. *Weed Science*. 1985 Mar;33(2):171-5.
- Yaduraju NT. Invasive Weeds in the tropics. In *Proceedings of the 19th Asian-Pacific Weed Science Society Conference, Manila, the Philippines, 17-21 March 2003* (pp. 59-68). Asian-Pacific Weed Science Society.

- Yamamoto A, Shim Is, Fujihara S, Yoneyama T, Usui K. Physiochemical factors affecting the salt tolerance of *Echinochloa crus-galli* Beauv. var. *formosensis* Ohwi. *Weed Biology and Management*. 2003 Jun;3(2):98-104.
- Ye XQ, Meng JL, Zeng B, Wu M, Zhang YY, Zhang XP. Submergence causes similar carbohydrate starvation but faster post-stress recovery than darkness in *Alternanthera philoxeroides* plants. *PLoS One*. 2016 Oct 24;11(10):e0165193.
- Zeng Q, Liu B, Gilna B, Zhang Y, Zhu C, Ma H, Pang J, Chen G, Zhu J. Elevated CO₂ effects on nutrient competition between a C₃ crop (*Oryza sativa* L.) and a C₄ weed (*Echinochloa crus-galli* L.). *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*. 2011 Jan;89(1):93-104.
- Ziska LH, George KA. Rising carbon dioxide and invasive, noxious plants: potential threats and consequences. *World Resource Review*. 2004 Nov 1;16(4):427-47.
- Ziska LH. *Climate Change Impacts on Weeds, Crop Systems and Global Change Laboratory. Climate Change and Agriculture: Promoting Practical and Profitable Responses*. 2010.
- Ziska LH, Caulfield FA. Rising CO₂ and pollen production of common ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.), a known allergy-inducing species: implications for public health. *Functional Plant Biology*. 2000;27(10):893-8.
- Ziska LH, Tomecek MB, Gealy DR. Competitive interactions between cultivated and red rice as a function of recent and projected increases in atmospheric carbon dioxide. *Agronomy Journal*. 2010 Jan;102(1):118-23.
- Ziska LH, Blumenthal DM, Franks SJ. Understanding the nexus of rising CO₂, climate change, and evolution in weed biology. *Invasive Plant Science and Management*. 2019 Jun;12(2):79-88.
- Ziska LH, Faulkner S, Lydon J. Changes in biomass and root: shoot ratio of field-grown Canada thistle (*Cirsium arvense*), a noxious, invasive weed, with elevated CO₂: implications for control with glyphosate. *Weed Science*. 2004 Aug;52(4):584-8.
- Ziska LH, Gealy DR, Tomecek MB, Jackson AK, Black HL. Recent and projected increases in atmospheric CO₂ concentration can enhance gene flow between wild and genetically altered rice (*Oryza sativa*). *PLoS One*. 2012 May 23;7(5):e37522.
- Ziska LH. The impact of elevated CO₂ on yield loss from a C₃ and C₄ weed in field-grown soybean. *Global Change Biology*. 2000 Dec;6(8):899-905.